

GLASS REINFORCED PLASTIC (GRP) PIPE COMPONENTS SUBJECTED TO VARIOUS LOADS

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Glass reinforced plastic pipes are increasingly used for chemical plant where corrosion is a problem. Design procedures which exist are recognised as being tentative. For metallic piping systems, there is much experience and background information for design to be reliable but similar necessary knowledge is not available for GRP pipes. The present investigation concerns the behaviour of piping tee-pieces and study is limited to in-plane flexural loads. To restrict the parameters, equal right-angled tee-joints for nominally 100 mm bore pipes of 2.4 kg/m² glass content only were used. The laminate was laid up by hand and consisted of E-glass as chopped strand mat with a matrix of the polyester resin Atlac 382-05. The form and quantity of reinforcement at the tee junction were the main parameters being investigated. Some tee-pieces were manufactured in industry and some in the laboratory. Each specimen consisted of a tee-piece, three straight lengths and three stub flanges. Strains and deformations were measured and tests were carried out to destruction. In interpreting the results, material tests on flat sheet material and lengths of straight pipes were carried out.

INTRODUCTION

The stress analysis of metallic piping components has been the subject of much interest in the chemical plant industry for many years. Any section of piping that has its temperature increased will tend to expand, although, in practice, restraints will exist at anchoring or support points. Consequently torsion and bending moments as well as direct and shear forces may be transmitted to the piping. The greater the flexibility of the pipeline the lower the moments and forces likely to exist, although flexibility is often only attained by introducing higher stresses in the pipe components. Design involves the balancing of strength and flexibility, whilst also taking into account other loading such as internal pressure, self weight and wind loading.

In order to assess the integrity of a pipeline it is necessary to have data on the stresses and flexibilities of each component likely to be used. For metallic piping components in common use a wealth of practical experience, experimental results and theoretical analyses exist and these are incorporated into design codes [1], [2]. For other materials a comparable knowledge is not available, although it is often assumed that similar expressions to those used for metallic piping are applicable.

More recently, glass reinforced plastic (GRP) pipes of various types have been used for chemical plant applications because of their corrosion resistance to certain fluids, which may otherwise attack components made from other materials including metals. Many different forms of GRP are available, produced by different manufacturing methods and starting materials, but the present work concerns hand lay-up of laminates from polyester resin and E glass in the form of chopped strand mat where there is a relatively high weight fraction of resin. Laminates of this kind are particularly useful where the maximum corrosion resistance is required. They are of low density and may be considered to be isotropic within the plane of lamination.

There is at present no accepted standard in the U.K. for the design of GRP pipelines and little information on their structural behaviour exists. The present work was initiated for this reason. It is restricted to a study of equal tee-pieces under in-plane bending loads, but it includes test data on straight pipes under different loading conditions and on strips cut from GRP flat plates.

Without the guidance of standard codes the design of pipelines incorporating GRP pipes and components is tentative and is usually based on the GRP vessel design code BS 4994 [3] together with relevant data from metallic piping codes such as BS 806 [1].

In most metallic pipe components the ductility is utilised in that localised stresses above yield may safely be allowed. For GRP, where behaviour is largely that of a brittle material, stresses under design conditions are kept very low, the basic philosophy being to try to ensure that there is a considerable margin between operating loads and those which would give rise to failure in tension. Tensile strains and forces per unit width of shell (in preference to stresses) are limited and, for this purpose, properties of extensibility and unit stress (force per unit width) based on glass reinforcement weight per unit area, are used rather than thickness. BS4994 assumes the values of extensibility and ultimate tensile unit stress to be constant over a range of weight fraction of glass, and hence assumes all stiffening and strengthening is derived from the glass.

Doubt exists about the stage at which a GRP pipe may be considered to have failed or, indeed, about how to define failure, although a limit of proportionality in the stress/strain curve is reported to exist close to 0.3% strain [4]. As in a preliminary investigation [5] the four following criteria of failure have been considered to try and correlate failure results in the present tests:-

- (a) onset of non-linearity of strain/load graph,
- (b) first audible cracking,
- (c) first visible damage,

(d) fracture.

It may be agreed that the different criteria are applicable to different uses of GRP. For chemical plant applications it is desirable that the material behaves linearly and that, in operation, criterion (a) is not reached since it would be indicative of significant irreversible damage. In [3] a strain limit of 0.2% is imposed while tensile unit stress is limited to an ultimate tensile unit stress divided by a factor depending upon the application, and which, for many applications and for comparison purposes later, is taken to be 10.

FLEXURE AND TORSION OF STRAIGHT PIPES

According to simple bending theory, when a moment M is applied over a short length dl of pipe, the change of slope of the centre line between the two ends, $d\phi$, is given by

$$d\phi = \frac{K M dl}{EI} \quad (1)$$

where EI is the flexural rigidity and $K = 1$. The same theory gives maximum stress, σ , by

$$\sigma = \frac{f M r_o}{I} \quad (2)$$

where r_o is the external radius and $f = 1$. The stress distribution is linear across the section and is greatest in value (σ_n) at the greatest distance from the neutral axis of bending.

A straight length of pipe subjected to a torsional moment, T , gives rise to maximum shear stresses (τ) on the outside surface in a plane tangential to the shell, the directions of the stresses being circumferential and axial and values being given by

$$\tau = \frac{T r_o}{J}$$

where J is the polar second moment of area.

The maximum tensile stress has the same value and acts on the outer surface on a helical line at 45° to the axis.

FLEXURE OF SMOOTH BENDS

When a smooth bend is subjected to a bending moment, ovalisation of the pipe section [6] occurs (see Fig. 1) in addition to the extension and compression of longitudinal generators (simple bending action). This leads to greater flexibility than that of a similar length of straight pipe, but also to a higher maximum stress than that calculated (σ_n) for the straight pipe. Equations (1) and (2) can still be applied but K (the flexibility factor) and f (the stress intensification factor) are greater than unity. Both factors are significant, can be determined theoretically, [7], [8] and largely depend on the parameter, $\lambda = Rt/r^2$, known as the pipe factor, but to a lesser extent on the ratio $\rho = r/R$.

A typical stress distribution is shown in Fig. 2 for in-plane bending. Hoop stresses are the most significant, have a large shell bending content and vary rapidly around the circumference.

The agreement between experimental results [9] and results of the best theoretical analyses [8] is generally good and limited experimental results [10] on GRP bends confirm that theoretical predictions are reliable.

FIG. 1 In-plane bending of smooth bend

FIG. 2 Typical stress ratio distribution for smooth bends [9]
 ($r = 80$ mm, $t = 5.15$ mm, $R = 228$ mm)

FLEXURE OF TEE PIECES

A pipe section in the vicinity of a tee junction under flexure ovalises in similar, but more complex, ways to that of a smooth bend. Because of the difficult geometry no reliable analysis is available. Design codes [1] incorporate empirical expressions for f in equation (2). They are based on experimental investigations for metal components. The expressions of BS 806 [1] have later been used to make comparisons with experimental results for GRP tees.

MATERIAL TESTS - STRIPS

During manufacture of each tee piece, a flat GRP sheet was laid-up so as to be representative of the tee piece in glass weight per unit area and resin content. Tee piece walls were of either 2.4 kg/m^2 or of 4.8 kg/m^2 construction and were all made from chopped strand mat, with a thin veil of glass on the outer surface.

Several different types of loading were applied to strips of each GRP sheet. In each test the object was to determine low loading (elastic) properties and stress as well as unit stress at the previously defined failure conditions (a) to (d). Tests carried out included tension, compression, four point bending, three point bending, lap shear strength tests, and tests to determine some of the through thickness properties. Details of the test methods used and full results are given in [11] and a brief account only is included here.

It may be shown that the laminate, if assumed homogeneous, would have five independent elastic constants, though the through thickness modulus and Poisson's ratio are usually ignored as having little relevance to practical structures. The same may not be said for the interlaminar shear modulus and in some cases interlaminar shear deformations and stresses may be significant. Accurate values could not be derived for interlaminar shear modulus. No satisfactory test exists for this quantity and estimates have been made from three point bend tests, from which values in the range 200 to 1000 MPa were extracted. Values of other properties from strip tests are given in Table 1. Small differences in elastic modulus values were detected between tension and compression tests for the 2.4 kg/m^2 plates, but not for the 4.8 kg/m^2 plates. It has been suggested by A.F. Johnson [12] that differences may arise due to different fibre stiffening actions under the two types of loading, but differences between the two values have been ignored later in this investigation in view of the results obtained.

More significant differences were detected between moduli from bending tests and those from ^{tension} tests on the 2.4 kg/m^2 plate. This has been attributed to the existence of surface resin-rich layers which may significantly reduce the bending stiffness compared to that recorded in tension. It is clear that under bending moments the distribution of reinforcement within a laminate will play a critical part in determining stiffness.

Differences between moduli recorded from four point bending tests and those recorded from three point bending tests were observed. These were attributed to the existence of shear deformations in the latter test, from which estimates of the interlaminar shear modulus (previously referred to) were made.

In the bending tests, deflections were generally recorded at several positions along the beam. The deflections so obtained give more accurate values of modulus than by simply using one recorded deflection relative to the position of a fixed anvil.

Ultimate compressive stress and ultimate compressive unit stress were, respectively, found to be significantly higher than ultimate tensile stress and ultimate tensile unit stress. Strengths were also found to be slightly higher in the four point bending tests than in tensile tests and strengths were significantly higher under three point bending than under four point bending. This may be attributed partly to non-linear distributions of stress across the beam and partly to a probability effect which may be significant in testing GRP components subjected to

Plate-glass content kg/m ²	Test	No. of specimens	Poisson Ratio	Modulus MPa E	Stress MPa				Extensibility X N/(mmkgm ⁻²)	Unit Stress N/(mmkgm ⁻²)			
					a	b	c	d		a	b	c	d
2.4	Tension	11	.377	9253	35.0	101	104	116.0	17120	64.8	194	209	215
2.4	Compression	10	.318	9940	-	-	-	-	18290	-	-	-	-
2.4	4 pt. Bend	18	.326	7438	38.3	85.0	77.0	119.9	14280	72.8	164	146	229
2.4	3 pt. Bend	8	-	Variable	70.6	134	107	175.9	Variable	135	252	199	335
4.8	Tension	6	.378	7863	24.2	79.7	88	88.4	18480	57.1	187	206	206
4.8	Compression	6	.342	7573	-	-	-	189.2	19970	-	-	-	499
4.8	4 pt. Bend	3	-	7905	49.8	73.4	65.6	104.8	19910	125	184	165	264
4.8	3 pt. Bend	7	-	Variable	59.4	91.8	77.9	125.7	Variable	145	219	193	302

TABLE 1 Summary of Strip Test Results

Manufacturer	Test	No. of specimens	Modulus E MPa	Stress MPa				Extensibility X N/(mmkgm ⁻²)	Unit Stress N/(mmkgm ⁻²)			
				a	b	c	d		a	b	c	d
CJK	Torsion	2	9860	15.1	-	52.9	74.2	22630	35.7	-	121	158.9
CJK	Compression	2	8583	-	-	-	156.5	17330	-	-	-	343.4
Industry	Torsion	6	8458	22.6	-	53.7	71.2	17650	47.4	-	111	149.6
"	Compression	4	8616	-	-	-	155.5	16680	-	-	-	316.1
"	Pressure	3	8200	25.0	55.7	61.7	84.5	20360	62.0	140	170	210.1
"	Tension	3	9375	-	-	-	-	20140	-	-	-	-
"	Cantilever	2	8783	57.8	43.3	110	134.8	16930	111	81.3	201	253.1

N.B. In most cases b was masked by noise from gripped section of tube.

TABLE 2 Summary of Pipe Test Results

complex stress distributions. The latter would arise because the smaller the volume of material under high stress the lower would be the chance of finding a local imperfection (e.g. a void) in that region to trigger failure. Consequently, as in the tests, mean failure stresses would be high and so would the scatter of the failure stresses.

MATERIAL TESTS - STRAIGHT PIPES

Straight pipes of both laboratory construction and industrial construction have been tested under a variety of different loadings. Details of experimental procedures and complete results are given by Kirk [11]. All pipes were constructed from nominally 2.4 kg/m² chopped strand glass mat and polyester resin. Uniform straight sections of piping were subjected to internal pressure (with zero axial stress), torsion and compression. Some sections of piping were also tested in tension but the continuation of such tests resulted in fracture at the ends and not in the gauge length. Sections of pipe which were flanged at both ends were subjected to cantilever bending tests. Because of the difficulties associated with constructing a flange, only industrially manufactured pipes could be used for this test.

Results of the tests are summarised in Table 2. Although fracture of specimens was not possible in every case, stresses, and unit stresses, have been estimated for the previously defined four criteria of 'failure' where this was possible.

As with the strip tests, the ultimate strength and ultimate unit stress were significantly higher for the compressive tests than for the open ended pressure tests which essentially gave hoop tensile conditions only. It was also found that the failure criteria (a), (b), (c) were difficult to estimate as very few signs of imminent fracture were detected.

The failure tensile stress and unit stress under torsional loading were found to be consistently between 70% and 80% of those under internal pressure loading. This indicates that failure is a result of complex action within the composite, though fracture was on a 45° helix consistent with an isotropic brittle material, see Fig. 3.

Results from all the pipe and strip tests generally show that a simple maximum tensile stress (or unit stress) failure envelope is not applicable to this material and the use of tensile test results could lead to overestimates of failure loads in structures where torsional loading is involved. This is in line with the results of Owen and Found [13] who demonstrated that, for a similar composite, none of the simple failure envelopes is applicable. Insufficient experimental results were available to construct a complete failure envelope. In the absence of this the results on tee pieces have been processed on the basis of a simple maximum tensile stress (or unit stress) failure envelope. The overall properties used for this purpose are given in Table 3.

TEE PIECE TESTS

Each specimen to be tested was manufactured from a tee piece (see Fig. 4a) attached by standard butt joints [14] to straight lengths, each of which was flanged at one end. The internal diameter of the piping was 100 mm throughout, the straight lengths having a nominal glass weight of 2.4 kg/m². The design parameters and measured dimensions are given in Table 4. Specimens 6 and 8 were industrially manufactured and the other specimens were manufactured in the laboratory.

Initially loading was applied incrementally in the rig shown in Fig. 4b. For all specimens except 1 and 6 strain gauges were attached to both internal and external surfaces. Gauge positions were generally parallel and perpendicular to the junction line although three gauge rosettes were used in certain positions. In order to minimise the number of gauges used, only one quadrant of the tee was

FIG. 3 Torsion fracture in straight pipe

FIG. 4 Tee piece
(a) before assembly
(b) in in-plane bending rig
(c) in alternative rig

FIG. 5 Measured stress distribution at tee junction under in-plane bending (tee 9)

FIG. 6 Interlaminar shear stress distribution at junction - estimated from experiment

Specimen	Mean radius (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Stiffness (kNm ²)	Estimated Failure Moments (kNm)			
				a	b	c	d
1	55.4	10.57	57.4	3.17	7.31	8.69	10.89
2	52.9	5.51	26.5	1.60	3.68	4.38	5.48
3	52.8	5.28	20.1	1.21	2.80	3.33	4.17
4	56.9	13.57	62.8	3.30	7.61	9.05	11.34
5	53.9	7.53	26.7	1.55	3.58	4.25	5.33
6	53.5	5.19	21.5	1.28	2.96	3.52	4.41
7	53.4	5.05	20.3	1.22	2.81	3.34	4.19
8	56.1	11.85	56.4	3.05	7.03	8.36	10.47
9	54.0	7.78	25.0	1.45	3.34	3.97	4.98

TABLE 3 Assumed Tee Piece Properties

Tee	L ₂ (mm)	Construction details	Glass weight per unit area of straight portion (kg/sq.m)	Mean thickness of straight portion (mm)	Ref
1 One piece double thickness	987		5.80 (nominally 4.8)	10.57	[5]
2 One piece unstiff- forced	987		3.08 (2.4)	5.51	[5]
3 One piece radius outside	987		2.35 (2.4)	5.28	[11]
4 One piece double thick- ness radius outside	835		5.85 (4.8)	13.57	[11]
5 As 3	835	As 3 except r _c = 30mm	2.93 (2.4)	7.53	[11]
6 Set on branch with scdble	835		2.42 (2.4)	5.19	[11]
7 As 6	987	As 6	2.30 (2.4)	5.05	[11]
8 As 4	835	As 4	5.50 (4.8)	11.85	[11]
9 One piece double radius	987		2.73 (2.4)	7.78	[11]

TABLE 4 Details of tee piece specimens tested

fully gauged. The specimens were initially tested to low loads (corresponding to less than 0.3% recorded strain) with flange A fixed and the load P_1 applied downwards (see Fig. 4b) at C. Repositioning of the specimen was then effected so that flange B was fixed at the base and then downward loads (P_2 of Fig. 4a in the new position) applied at C. From the strain results, stress distributions were calculated. A typical distribution of stress ratios (stress/ σ_n) is plotted in Fig. 5.

At the same time as strain values were recorded, deflections of the pipes were measured and compared with calculated centre line deflections. These are compared for some of the specimens in [5], [10] and [11].

After the initial low load tests, each specimen was tested to fracture. In some cases fractures occurred which left the tee pieces intact. The specimen was then transferred to the rig of Fig. 4c for final fracture. Here the direction of loading was so as to give a moment of the same sense on the tee piece as had been acting in the previous rig (Fig. 4b) in the failure test. In each test, loads corresponding to the four previously defined failure criteria (a) to (d) were recorded.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS FOR TEE PIECE TESTS

The stress distribution given in Fig. 5 was typical and although absolute values varied for different tests, the overall shapes were similar. The maximum positive and negative values of stress ratio measured for all specimens are given in Table 5.

The stress distributions and stress intensification factors measured were independent of loading direction and appeared to be very similar for the two rigs (Figs. 4b and 4c), though some degradation can always be assumed to have occurred before the specimen was transferred to the rig of Fig. 4c.

Because of the finite gauge length of the strain gauges (2 mm and 3 mm were used) and because it is not possible to predict the exact position of maximum stress, stress intensification factors higher than those quoted will exist. However, those recorded are lower, generally by a considerable margin, than the values calculated by the empirical formula of BS 806. The low measured values can partly be attributed to the natural overlapping of mats at the tee junction as well as to any extra mat applied as reinforcement during construction. The current design codes for metallic piping, e.g. [1], do not allow for the use of such shapes of reinforcement as those used here, except where pads or saddles are welded on. Tees 6 and 8 have been regarded as equivalent to welded on pad reinforced tees in comparing results. Tees 3, 4, 5 and 7 do bear some similarity to welding tees and it would appear reasonable to use the formula in [1] corresponding to this type of metal tee piece. The expressions given currently in [1] for welding tees were found to lead to underestimates of stresses for certain of the specimens and an expression giving stress intensification factors between those for the two types mentioned in [1] may be appropriate.

The centre line deflection at the loaded end of each specimen was calculated on the assumption that the pipe section remained constant throughout and that no additional flexibility occurred due to ovalisation. In all cases experimental measurements in the linear loading range were lower than the corresponding calculated values [1]. If the same assumptions were made in pipe layout calculations, the anchor reactions would be underestimated. Better agreement was given between theoretical and experimental values when allowance was made in the calculations for pipe thickening in the vicinity of butt joints and in the thicker tee pieces. No allowance, however, was made for local reinforcement as in some of the tee pieces and it appears reasonable to take $K = 1$ in equation (1) provided due account is taken of realistic thicknesses along the pipe. Reinforcement in the form of saddles is more extensive than 'local' and it is suggested that the tee is assumed rigid for a length of one pipe radius along each pipe from the intersection of the centre lines.

Tee	Stress Intensification Factor (SIF)	
	Maximum measured	BS 806 formulae
1	1.10 ⁺	4.13
2	4.50	6.21
3	2.20	6.38
4	1.38	3.55
5	2.00	5.10
6	1.58 ⁺	3.56*
7	0.72	3.49*
8	2.00	3.85
9	2.28	4.21

Key. Values are given relative to a straight pipe of the same general construction as the tee (e.g. 2.4 kg/m²).

* Specimens 6 and 7 have been treated as pad (or saddle) reinforced tees with pad thicknesses of 5.78 mm and 6.01 mm respectively.

+ Specimens 1 and 6 had outside gauges only.

TABLE 5 Maximum Elastic Stress Intensification Factors

Specimen	Rig	Relative Strength Factors			
		a	b	c	d
1 ⁺	Fig. 4b	-	5.01	-	< 2.38
	Fig. 4c	2.33	-	5.20	< 4.69
2	Fig. 4b	1.95	3.26	-	< 2.95
	Fig. 4c	-	-	4.13	3.54
3	Fig. 4b	.852	2.25	.933	< .813
	Fig. 4c	-	-	-	1.42
4	Fig. 4b	1.68	3.56	< 1.80	< 2.25
	Fig. 4c	-	-	1.82	< 2.05
5	Fig. 4b	1.46	2.62	< 1.28	< 1.60
	Fig. 4c	-	-	< 1.32	< 1.66
6 ⁺	Fig. 4b	1.00	1.68	.774	< .792
	Fig. 4c	-	-	-	1.43
7	Fig. 4b	.775	1.68	1.11	.813
8	Fig. 4b	1.78	6.64	< 1.97	< 2.46
	Fig. 4c	-	-	< 2.85	< 3.57
9	Fig. 4b	1.40	1.73	1.46	1.26

Key. All figures are given relative to a straight pipe of the same general construction as the tee piece (e.g. 2.4 kg/m²).

+ Specimens 1 and 6 had outside gauges only.

TABLE 6 Estimated Relative Strength Factors

From the properties given in Table 3 it is possible to calculate expected failure moments (failure being defined as (a) to (d)) for straight pipes of the same weight of glass per unit area as each tee piece. Dividing these values by the moments at failure of each tee piece gives relative strength factors for the four criteria of failure. These values are given in Table 6.

Agreement between relative strength factors and stress intensification factors (either measured values or those derived from the formula in BS 806) would be surprising as it would infer perfect linearity up to failure and that the material fails according to a maximum direct stress criterion.

Bearing in mind these limitations and the difficulty in detecting the failure of the component, some agreement is evident between relative strength factors and stress intensification factors. The tees of nominally 4.8 kg/m^2 (tees 1, 4, 7) were not taken to fracture, as fracture occurred away from the tee piece as did tee 5. This, with the results of the strain gauge tests, shows the usefulness of these tees, although visible delamination occurred on tee 1 at a relatively low moment.

The appearance of delaminations (mainly on tees 1, 2, 3) shows an inherent weakness of laminates to interlaminar shear. Using the strain gauge results it is possible to estimate and plot the variation in shear stress in the ∇ direction (Fig. 4a) due to changing shell bending moment (see Fig. 6). Using an interlaminar shear strength of 7 MPa (given in [3]), which is probably low, and the given distribution of Fig. 7, which ignores any shear stresses in the ψ direction, together with measured thicknesses [1] shows that shear failure may be expected at a moment of 3.97 kNm compared with the recorded values in Table 6.

This type of material failure is currently not considered in the design procedures and may be significant at junctions of shells or where other localised bending moments occur. To counteract this effect an overall thickening up of the component may be best, although the use of thickening without fillet radii at the intersection may localise the bending moments to a greater extent, thus producing delamination as in tee 1.

The tees of 2.4 kg/m^2 showed fairly similar relative strength factors except for tee 2 (no reinforcement) with considerably lower values. This confirms the value of applying reinforcement local to the junction line to reduce the normal stresses in the laminate. Although the industrial tees, which were reinforced with a non-integral saddle of GRP, showed low elastic stress intensification factors, they did not show as high relative strength factors as may have been expected. This was attributed to the construction being susceptible to adhesive failure between the main laminate and the reinforcing overlay.

Tee 9, which had both internal and external fillet radii at the crotch, showed very similar characteristics to the tees with an internally square intersection combined with an external fillet radius. This type of tee may therefore be useful but it may prove difficult to manufacture unless specially shaped moulds were available.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The tests on tees at low loads where there was a sensibly linear response show that, along the intersection lines,
 - (i) stress distributions are complex,
 - (ii) maximum stresses are likely to be on the inner surface where the resin is purposely unreinforced by glass for corrosion purposes,
 - (iii) maximum measured normal stresses are not as excessive as is suggested by empirical formulae used in design codes, e.g. BS 806,
 - (iv) stresses are largely due to shell bending,
 - (v) interlaminar shear stresses may be significant due to the high bending stress gradients.

2. Deflection measurements at low loads suggest that, in pipeline flexibility calculations, anchor reactions could be underestimated if the full thickness of pipes were not taken into consideration at butt joints and at tee pieces reinforced over the complete length.
3. Tests to fracture (or attempted fracture) on the different tees showed
 - (i) internal cracks corresponding to high measured stresses,
 - (ii) interlaminar shear at positions corresponding to particularly high bending stress gradients,
 - (iii) butt joints often fracture before the tee piece itself,
 - (iv) design moments based on either load or strain limitation were, for every specimen, appreciably lower than fracture moments, or indeed than the moments at failure defined according to criteria (a), (b) or (c).
4. For use with 2.4 kg/m^2 straight pipes, the 2.4 kg/m^2 tees with external fillet radius with or without internal fillet radius would be most satisfactory for the type of loading assumed, and bearing in mind economy in the use of material. The 4.8 kg/m^2 tees with external fillet radius are satisfactory for load bearing though there is doubt about strength if no external fillet radius is present. Saddle reinforcement may be satisfactory, but doubt about the integrity arises because of the adhesion between pipe and saddle. The lowest fracture moment occurred with the 2.4 kg/m^2 tee piece with no reinforcement.

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